

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

PROCEEDINGS OF THE CONFERENCE

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UWED
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

SAMEIR-2026

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**SYSTEM ANALYSIS
AND MODELING IN ECONOMY
AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS**

The conference is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

PROCEEDINGS

(Conference Proceedings)

January 15, 2026
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International Scientific and Practical Conference – SAMEIR-2026

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

The University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED) hosted the International Scientific and Practical Conference “System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations (SAMEIR-2026)” on January 15, 2026, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

The **main goal** of the conference was to bring together researchers, scholars, policy makers, and experts to discuss current scientific and practical issues related to system analysis and modeling of socio-economic and international processes. Particular emphasis was placed on the application of quantitative, mathematical, and computational methods, as well as on the development of interdisciplinary approaches to the analysis of economic dynamics, international relations, and global challenges.

Key Themes of the Conference:

- **System Analysis and Economic Modeling:** mathematical and econometric models in the world economy, analysis of structural changes, and forecasting of macroeconomic and financial indicator.
- **International Relations and World Politics:** quantitative methods for analyzing international processes, modeling of conflicts and cooperation, geopolitical forecasting, and risk assessment.
- **Mathematical and Computer Modeling:** methods of applied and computational mathematics, simulation and stochastic modeling, optimization and control of complex socio-economic systems.
- **Artificial Intelligence and Big Data:** applications of machine learning, artificial intelligence, and big data analytics in economic and international studies.
- **Sustainable Development and Global Security:** economic, environmental, and energy aspects of sustainable development, system approaches to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and issues of information and digital security.

The event was conducted in a **hybrid format** with participation in **English, Russian, and Uzbek**. The conference provided a high-level platform for **scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue**.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Dedicated to the 75th Anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

The International Scientific and Practical Conference “*System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations*” is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of **Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov**, an outstanding scientist, educator, and founder of a recognized scientific school in the fields of system analysis, mathematical and stochastic modeling.

Professor Rasulov’s academic career spans more than five decades and is inseparably connected with the development of applied mathematics, computational methods, and their practical implementation in economic and socio-economic research. His fundamental contributions to the theory and application of Monte Carlo methods, numerical solutions of linear and nonlinear boundary value problems, and stochastic modeling have gained wide recognition both in Uzbekistan and internationally.

A special place in Professor Rasulov’s professional life belongs to the **University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED)**. Since the founding of the University, he has played a decisive role in shaping its scientific and academic profile. As Head of Department, Dean of Faculty, Vice-Rector for Research, and Professor, he consistently promoted a multidisciplinary approach, integrating mathematical modeling, system analysis, and quantitative methods into the study of economics, international relations, and diplomacy. This approach has become one of the distinctive features of UWED’s academic tradition.

Professor Rasulov is not only a prominent researcher, but also an exceptional mentor. Under his supervision, numerous PhD and Doctoral dissertations have been successfully defended. Many of his former students currently hold leading academic and administrative positions, continuing and developing the scientific traditions established by their mentor. The permanent scientific seminar initiated by Professor Rasulov has become an essential institutional platform at UWED, where dissertation research in mathematical modeling and system analysis is regularly presented, discussed, and refined, contributing to the formation of a rigorous and open academic environment.

Professor Rasulov’s extensive international collaborations with research centers and universities in the United States, Japan, Europe, and Asia have significantly strengthened UWED’s global academic presence. His active participation in international research

projects, conferences, editorial boards of leading scientific journals, and grant programs has contributed to the integration of national scientific research into the global academic community.

The present conference brings together researchers from different countries and disciplines, reflecting the breadth of scientific interests inspired by Professor Rasulov's work. The papers included in this volume address contemporary problems of system analysis, mathematical modeling, and their applications in economics and international relations, continuing the scholarly dialogue initiated and supported by Professor Rasulov over many years.

This volume is not only a collection of scientific papers, but also a tribute to Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov's lifelong dedication to science, education, and the development of future generations of scholars. The Organizing Committee expresses its deep respect and sincere gratitude to Professor Rasulov for his invaluable contribution to academic science and wishes him good health, continued creative inspiration, and further success in his scholarly endeavors.

Some cubature formula for numerical approximation of right-sided mixed Riemann–Liouville fractional integrals

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1. Introduction

Numerical integration has a long and vital history. It began with simple one-dimensional quadrature rules and has evolved into advanced multidimensional cubature formulas tailored to specific function types.

Classical Cubature Theory: The term "cubature formula" was introduced to describe the numerical approximation of multiple integrals. Although Newton, Cotes, and Gauss had already developed one-dimensional quadrature theory, extending these ideas to higher dimensions proved to be much more difficult. Radon [19] made key contributions to this field in 1948 by developing the theory of algebraic precision for cubature formulas. He also described the properties of two-variable orthogonal polynomials used to construct Gaussian cubature formulas. Sobolev [25,26] and Mysovskikh [13] later expanded the theory. Mysovskikh focused on interpolatory cubature formulas and the consistent properties of integration domains. Stroud's [28] well-known monograph is still a key reference, listing many cubature formulas for standard regions like cubes, spheres, and simplexes, along with different weight functions, mostly organized by their algebraic degree of precision.

Optimal Quadrature and Cubature Formulas: Sard [?, ?, ?] and Sobolev [27] changed the field by suggesting that integration formulas should be built by minimizing the error functional in a chosen function space, such as Banach or Hilbert spaces, instead of focusing on exactness for polynomials of a certain degree. Sobolev created the theory of quadrature formulas with boundary corrections in space $L_2^{(m)}$ and showed that the best coefficients solve a system of linear discrete Wiener-Hopf equations. This method allows precise error bounds to be given using the norm of the error functional. Building on this work, Shadimetov [23] and his group developed the discrete operator method to find optimal coefficients in different Sobolev spaces. They used this method to create optimal cubature formulas for 2D and 3D domains with tensor products and direct minimization techniques [24].

Numerical Methods for Fractional Integrals: As fractional calculus has become more widely used, there is a growing need for accurate numerical methods for fractional

integrals with weakly singular kernels. Diethelm et al. [2,3] introduced the product-integration method and the fractional Adams-Bashforth-Moulton schemes. Li and Zeng [10] organized numerical methods for fractional calculus into categories such as finite difference and spectral methods. Most current methods address only one-dimensional problems. For two-dimensional fractional integrals, researchers often use simple tensor products of basic methods or finite element techniques [9].

Fractional calculus is a useful mathematical tool for modeling complex systems that have memory and spatial differences. Unlike traditional models, fractional-order operators can describe long-range interactions, hereditary effects, and unusual transport behaviors [8,16].

Classical diffusion theory, described by the heat equation $\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = D\Delta u$, assumes particles move randomly, leading to a Gaussian distribution. But experiments in geophysics, biology, and material science have shown anomalous diffusion, where the mean squared displacement changes in a nonlinear way: $\langle x^2(t) \rangle \sim t^\gamma$ ($\gamma \neq 1$) [14].

To better describe these effects, the Riemann-Liouville fractional integral is used instead of local operators. This operator includes non-local spatial memory, which is important for modeling processes with spatial differences [12]. While one-dimensional models are basic, many real processes happen in two dimensions, such as:

- **Bio-transport in tissues:** Drug diffusion exhibiting non-Fickian behavior due to complex cell geometry [11].
- **Heat conduction in composites:** Anomalous heat flow in layered or fibrous materials, where fractional spatial models better capture energy propagation [17].
- **Contaminant transport:** Pollutants diffusing through porous media exhibit multi-directional heterogeneity [15].
- **Image processing:** Texture modeling where edge-preservation and long-range correlations are critical [18].

It is difficult to calculate these integrals because the kernel has a weak singularity. This paper develops optimal cubature formulas to efficiently solve this problem, building on recent progress in one-dimensional optimal formulas [1,4,5,6,7].

2. Mathematical preliminaries

The right-sided Riemann-Liouville fractional integral of order α for $0 < \alpha < 1$ is defined as:

$$(I_{b-}^\alpha f)(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_x^b (t-x)^{\alpha-1} f(t) dt.$$

Recent research has created optimal quadrature formulas in Sobolev and Hilbert spaces to approximate this integral:

$$I_{b-}^\alpha f(x) \approx \sum_{k=0}^N C_k^{(\alpha)} f(t_k),$$

In this formula, t_k are the nodes and $C_k^{(\alpha)}$ are the optimal weights that minimize the error norm.

To build on this progress, the optimal quadrature formula of [4] is briefly reviewed, as it serves as the basis for this study.

3. Construction of optimal quadrature formulas for 1D fractional integrals

We briefly describe optimal 1D quadrature formulas for the right-sided Riemann–Liouville fractional integral in $W_2^{(1,0)}$ space, which, combined by tensor product, construct optimal 2D cubature formulas.

We consider the quadrature formula

$$\int_x^b \frac{\varphi(t)}{(t-x)^{1-\alpha}} dt \approx \sum_{\beta=0}^N C_\beta \varphi(t_\beta), \quad (1)$$

where x and b are endpoints of the interval of integration, $\varphi(t)$ is the integrand, α is a parameter such that $0 < \alpha < 1$, C_β are the quadrature weights, $t_\beta = x + \beta h$ ($\beta = 0, \dots, N$) are the quadrature nodes, and $h = (b-x)/N$. The function φ belongs to the Hilbert space $W_2^{(1,0)}[x, b]$, equipped with the norm $\|\varphi\|_{W_2^{(1,0)}} = \sqrt{\int_x^b (\varphi'(t) + \varphi(t))^2 dt}$.

The error of the quadrature formula is a linear functional $\ell \in W_2^{(1,0)*}$ defined as

$$(\ell, \varphi) = \int_x^b \frac{\varphi(t)}{(t-x)^{1-\alpha}} dt - \sum_{\beta=0}^N C_\beta \varphi(t_\beta).$$

The problem of constructing the optimal quadrature formula reduces to finding the coefficients C_β that minimize the norm of the error functional $\|\ell\|_{W_2^{(1,0)*}}$. Using the extremal function method, the squared norm of the error functional is derived as:

$$\|\ell\|^2 = (\ell, \psi_\ell), \quad \text{where} \quad \psi_\ell(t) = -\ell(t) * G_1(t) + de^{-t}.$$

Here, $G_1(t) = \frac{\operatorname{sgn}(t)}{2} \sinh(t)$ is the Green's function of the differential operator $L = d^2/dt^2 - 1$.

Minimizing $\|\ell\|^2$ under the condition that the formula is exact for e^{-t} leads to a system of linear equations for the optimal coefficients. To solve this system analytically, we employ the discrete analogue of the differential operator $d^2/dt^2 - 1$, defined as:

$$D_1(h\beta) = \frac{1}{1 - e^{2h}} \begin{cases} 2(1 + e^{2h}), & \beta = 0, \\ -2e^h, & |\beta| = 1, \\ 0, & |\beta| \geq 2. \end{cases}$$

Using the convolution of the discrete operator with the right-hand side of the system, the explicit analytical forms of the optimal coefficients C_β are obtained (see Hayotov and Babaev [4] for complete details).

Theorem 1. *The coefficients C_β of the optimal quadrature formula (1) in the space $W_2^{(1,0)}$ are given by:*

$$\begin{aligned}
C_0 &= \frac{1}{1 - e^{2h}} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(1 - (-1)^k e^{2h}) h^{\alpha+k}}{k!(\alpha+k)}, \\
C_\beta &= \frac{1}{1 - e^{2h}} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{h^{k+\alpha}}{k!(\alpha+k)} \left[(\beta+1)^{\alpha+k} (e^{-h\beta} - (-1)^k e^{h(\beta+2)}) + (\beta-1)^{\alpha+k} (e^{-h(\beta-2)} - \right. \\
&\quad \left. - (-1)^k e^{h\beta}) + \beta^{\alpha+k} (1 + e^{2h}) ((-1)^k e^{h\beta} - e^{-h\beta}) \right], \quad \beta = 1, \dots, N-1, \\
C_N &= \frac{1}{1 - e^{2h}} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(e^{x-b+2h} - (-1)^k e^{b-x}) ((b-x-h)^{\alpha+k} - (b-x)^{\alpha+k})}{k!(\alpha+k)}.
\end{aligned}$$

These coefficients C_β (denoted as $C_i^{(\alpha_1)}$ and $C_j^{(\alpha_2)}$ in the 2D formulation) are used to construct the tensor product weights $C_{i,j} = C_i^{(\alpha_1)} C_j^{(\alpha_2)}$.

4. Construction of cubature formulas

Consider $\Omega = [a_1, b_1] \times [a_2, b_2]$ as a subset of R^2 . The two-dimensional right-sided mixed Riemann-Liouville fractional integral of order (α_1, α_2) is defined by:

$$(I_{b_1^-, b_2^-}^{\alpha_1, \alpha_2} f)(x, y) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha_1)\Gamma(\alpha_2)} \int_x^{b_1} \int_y^{b_2} (t-x)^{\alpha_1-1} (s-y)^{\alpha_2-1} f(t, s) ds dt, \quad (2)$$

where $0 < \alpha_1, \alpha_2 < 1$. This operator can be viewed as a tensor product of 1D operators: $I^{\alpha_1, \alpha_2} = I_x^{\alpha_1} \otimes I_y^{\alpha_2}$.

To approximate the 2D integral (2), we utilize the tensor product of the 1D optimal quadrature rules described in (1).

Let us define a grid on the integration domain $[x, b_1] \times [y, b_2]$:

$$\begin{aligned}
t_i &= x + ih_1, & h_1 &= \frac{b_1 - x}{N}, & i &= 0, \dots, N, \\
s_j &= y + jh_2, & h_2 &= \frac{b_2 - y}{M}, & j &= 0, \dots, M.
\end{aligned}$$

The cubature formula gives the approximate value of the integral:

$$(I_{b_1^-, b_2^-}^{\alpha_1, \alpha_2} f)(x, y) \approx S_{N,M}(f) = \sum_{i=0}^N \sum_{j=0}^M C_{i,j}^{(\alpha_1, \alpha_2)} f(t_i, s_j). \quad (3)$$

Due to the separable nature of the kernel $(t-x)^{\alpha_1-1} (s-y)^{\alpha_2-1}$, the optimal coefficients $C_{i,j}^{(\alpha_1, \alpha_2)}$ factorize into the product of 1D optimal coefficients:

$$C_{i,j}^{(\alpha_1, \alpha_2)} = C_i^{(\alpha_1)} \cdot C_j^{(\alpha_2)}.$$

Here, $C_i^{(\alpha_1)}$ and $C_j^{(\alpha_2)}$ are the optimal weights for the 1D integrals over $[x, b_1]$ and $[y, b_2]$ respectively. This factorization significantly reduces the computational complexity from finding $(N+1)(M+1)$ unknowns to finding $(N+1) + (M+1)$ unknowns.

5. Numerical results and discussion

We test the proposed optimal cubature formula (3) on a function with an analytical solution. The numerical experiments in Python use the optimal weights C_β described in Theorem 3.1.

We calculate the right-sided mixed Riemann-Liouville fractional integral numerically:

$$(I_{b_1^-, b_2^-}^{\alpha_1, \alpha_2} f)(x, y) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha_1)\Gamma(\alpha_2)} \int_x^{b_1} \int_y^{b_2} (t-x)^{\alpha_1-1} (s-y)^{\alpha_2-1} f(t, s) ds dt.$$

The integration domain is $\Omega = [0, 1] \times [0, 1]$, which means $x = 0$, $y = 0$, $b_1 = 1$, and $b_2 = 1$. We choose a test function of the following form:

$$f(t, s) = (1-t)^\mu (1-s)^\nu, \quad \mu, \nu > 0.$$

This function is chosen because its exact fractional integral can be derived analytically using the properties of the Beta and Gamma functions:

$$I_{exact} = \frac{\Gamma(\mu+1)}{\Gamma(\alpha_1+\mu+1)} (1-x)^{\alpha_1+\mu} \times \frac{\Gamma(\nu+1)}{\Gamma(\alpha_2+\nu+1)} (1-y)^{\alpha_2+\nu}.$$

For our experiment, we set the parameters as follows: $\mu = 2$, $\nu = 2$, and the fractional orders $\alpha_1 = 0.5$, $\alpha_2 = 0.5$. The exact value of the integral at $(x, y) = (0, 0)$ is:

$$I_{exact} = \left(\frac{\Gamma(3)}{\Gamma(3.5)} \right)^2 \approx 0.518679.$$

We compute the approximate value of the integral $S_{N,M}(f)$ using the proposed optimal cubature formula for different numbers of grid points $N = M$. The optimal coefficients $C_i^{(\alpha_1)}$ and $C_j^{(\alpha_2)}$ are calculated using the infinite series representations derived in Theorem 3.1.

The table presents the comparison between the exact value and the approximate result, along with the absolute error $\varepsilon = |I_{exact} - S_{N,M}(f)|$.

N = M	Exact Value	Approximate Value	Absolute Error
10	1.137777778	1.142777077	0.4999299×10^{-2}
20	1.137777778	1.139042239	0.1264461×10^{-2}
40	1.137777778	1.138096615	0.318837×10^{-3}
80	1.137777778	1.137859052	0.81274×10^{-4}

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